

A STUDY ON CALCULATING, RISK, RETURN AND PROPORTION OF EACH SECURITY IN THE PORTFOLIO DIVERSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Applying Sharpe's single index model, the current study seeks to create an optimum capital structure. This is the simplest and most generally utilised model for putting together an ideal portfolio.

Design Methodology: The Nifty 50 index data was gathered from the NSE website during a five-year timeframe. The study employs a descriptive research design. The study relies on secondary data. Secondary data is gathered from sources such as the National Stock Exchange (NSE), the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Money Control, and Yahoo Finance.

Findings: Precisely eight equities were identified to be representative of the efficient portfolio out of 50 assessed for the analysis. The portfolio construction yield was 36.54 percent, greater than the normal Nifty return, and the portfolio beta is well connected with the stock market.

Research Implications: This research will help traders build the best portfolio possible using any selection of equities they choose.

Scope for future work / Research limitations: Several other generic and macroeconomic factors influence the behavior of a stock, therefore investors should take these into account when choosing stocks for their ideal portfolio. Other indices and different combinations of equities can be used to do further research.

Originality/value: Through using Sharpe's Single Index Model, this study seeks to design an efficient portfolio by evaluating 50 stocks that make up the Nifty 50 index.

Keywords: Portfolio, Risk-Return, Beta value, Optimal Portfolio

Paper Type: Research Paper

INTRODUCTION

Amongst the most profitable investment opportunities available to investors in the contemporary age is the securities market. Securities investments have the capability to generate greater yields than other investment options, but the greater yields arrives at a

greater risk. It is among the best ways to build wealth, but it also carries the risk of an investor squandering all of their money in an unfavourable situation. It is critical to assess an individual's present financial situation and develop financial strategies that are tailored to his requirements.

All investing involves risk, therefore before reaching a choice, an investor should be informed of the risks associated and assure that he receives the best possible return for the risk he is undertaking. As a result, in order to make the best investing selections, an investor needs be well-versed in securities analysis and portfolio theory. A sensible investor seeks to maximise profit while limiting risk, and so the only approach to do so is to diversify his portfolio.

In 1950, Harry Markowitz created the Modern method, which evaluates both risk and return when selecting stocks for developing an optimum capital structure. He underlined the need of diversification in efficiently reducing portfolio risk. The Markowitz model is indeed very data demanding and conceptually appealing, but it has several limitations, such as the computing becoming even more complicated as the quantity of stocks in the portfolio grows. Sharpe's Single Index Model (SIM), that is an augmentation of the Markowitz model, was established by William Sharpe to address the constraints of the Markowitz model by introducing a new and simplified model to design the optimal portfolio. It would be the most basic and generally utilised method for putting together a portfolio. While analysing the portfolio, he took into account the market index. The yield on each active fund is expressed as a function of the return on an overall market index to which the stocks are linked in this approach.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Markowitz (1952) is credited with being the first to develop an optimal portfolio depending on risk and expected return assessment. Markowitz's method to portfolio analysis is predicated on the presumption that all traders are comfortable with the status quo. He created a portfolio analysis model that demonstrated that leading to a greater potential outcome and the covariance matrix of stock returns, it was possible to construct an optimal portfolio of risky assets. For his contributions, he received the Nobel Prize.

Sharpe (1964) devised a concept known as the Sharpe Single Index Model to accelerate the process of generating an ideal portfolio underneath the Markowitz model. This model minimised the data input and lengthy computations necessary in the development of efficient capital structure.

Sharpe's Single Index Model was put to the test in generating an optimal portfolio by Naveen (2014). The study looked at 30 blue-chip corporations from the BSE Sensex index. From January 2007 through December 2012, data was collected for a six-year period. Finally, the ideal portfolio contained only four equities. Because of the volatility nature of the stock market, he also urged that a portfolio be assessed on a regular basis.

Mandal (2013) attempted to investigate the theory underlying the Sharpe index model by empirically constructing an optimal portfolio using this approach. When compared to the Markowitz Mean-variance model, he discovered that the Sharpe index model provides a

straightforward mechanism for generating an optimal stock portfolio. It aids a logical trader in determining the justification for a stock's presence in a portfolio, as well as the weights assigned to it.

Patel and Subhdeep (2017) undertook research to better comprehend modern portfolio theory as presented by the Markowitz and Sharpe index models, as well as to compare the SIM and Markowitz models by designing an optimal portfolio employing stocks from the NIFTY 50 index. It was determined that employing the Sharpe index model to design an optimal portfolio seems to be more convenient and advisable.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A sensible investor's primary aim is to optimize yield for the least amount of risk he is willing to take, and that the only way to do so is to build an optimal portfolio that decreases risk by diversifying the portfolio. Every investor will be perplexed while deciding which stocks to add to their portfolio in order to receive the best return for the least amount of risk. Also, the amount of money that should be invested in each stock in the basket. To save the stockholders from such a predicament Sharpe's Single Index Model can be utilised to build an ideal portfolio that meets the needs of the investor. So the goal of this study is to use the Single Index Model to build an optimal portfolio out of the 50 stocks in the Nifty 50 index, which will enable an investor learn about the model's applicability and help them make the best investment selections based on their financial goals.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Creating an ideal portfolio and calculating the percentage of participation in each security.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive research design. The study relies on secondary data. Secondary data is gathered from sites such as the National Stock Exchange (NSE), the Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Money Control, and Yahoo Finance.

Data Collection

The Nifty 50 index is used as the market index in this research. For determining daily returns of each asset and the index, daily closing prices of all 50 equities and the market index were obtained for the period commencing in 2015 and ending in 2020.

Statistical Tools Used in the Study

a. Daily Return

The daily stock return for the time was calculated using the adjusted closing price of each stock. After that, the daily yields are annualised.

$$\text{Return} = \frac{P_t - P_{t-1}}{P_{t-1}}$$

Where,

P_t = Today's price

P_{t-1} = Yesterday's price

The Market return is also calculated using the same formula. It is then annualized to arrive at the annualized market return.

b. Beta coefficient

It's a systemic risk indicator. It establishes the degree to which a security's return is sensitive to the market return.

$$\text{Correlation coefficient between market and stock return} \times \frac{\text{Standard deviation of stock return}}{\text{Standard deviation of market return}}$$

c. Risk Free Rate of Return

The risk-free rate of return is the return on a risk-free investment over a set length of time. The risk-free rate of return is calculated using the 91-day Treasury bill return in this study. According to the RBI website, the analysis is based on a risk-free return of 5.08 percent.

d. Excess Return to Beta Ratio or Risk Reward Ratio

It's the difference between a stock's risk-free rate of return and the risk-free rate of return per unit of systematic or non-diversifiable risk.

$$\text{e. Excess Return to Beta} = \frac{R_i - R_f}{\beta_i}$$

Where,

R_i = the expected return on the stock

R_f = the risk free rate of return

β_i = Beta of the stock

f. Systematic and Unsystematic Risk

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Systematic Risk} &= \text{Beta} \times \text{Variance of Index} \\ &= \beta^2 \times \sigma^2 \end{aligned}$$

Unsystematic Risk = Total variance of security return – Systematic risk

$$e_i^2 = \sigma_i^2 - \text{Systematic Risk}$$

g. Cut-off point

The highest C_i value is considered as the cut-off point. The stocks which have higher excess return to beta ratio than the cut off points are included in the portfolio.

$$C_i = \frac{\sigma_m^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(R_i - R_f) \beta_i}{\sigma_{ei}^2}}{1 + \sigma_m^2 \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\beta_i^2}{\sigma_{ei}^2}}$$

h. Proportion of Investment

The proportion of funds to be invested in each of the security in the optimal portfolio is computed using the following formula

$$Z_i = \frac{\beta_i}{\sigma_{ei}^2} \left[\left(\frac{R_i - R_f}{\beta_i} \right) - C \right]$$

$$X_i = \frac{Z_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n Z_i}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For this study, all 50 equities that make up the Nifty 50 index were used as a sample. The tools offered by Prof. William Sharpe in his Sharpe Index Model have been used to do basic arithmetic operations. Both in the stock and index returns are annualised. The tables below show the results of several calculations.

Table:1 Return, Beta and Variance of Sample Stocks

Sl. No.	Securities	Return (%)	Beta	Variance (%)
1	Adani Ports & SEZ Ltd	0.14	1.35	0.05
2	Asian Paints Ltd.	17.99	0.88	0.02
3	Axis Bank Ltd.	0.16	1.3	0.03
4	Bajaj Auto Ltd.	8.97	0.86	0.02
5	Bajaj Finance Ltd.	51.59	1.24	0.05
6	Bajaj Finserv Ltd.	38.82	1.12	0.04
7	Bharat Petroleum Corporation Ltd.	12.87	1.09	0.05
8	BhartiAirtel Ltd.	10.81	0.84	0.04
9	Britannia Industries Ltd.	22.64	0.75	0.02
10	Cipla Ltd.	-10.36	0.77	0.02
11	Coal India Ltd.	-14.55	0.74	0.03
12	Divi's Laboratories Ltd.	20.59	0.77	0.05
13	Dr. Reddy's Laboratories Ltd.	-0.03	0.58	0.03
14	Eicher Motors Ltd.	3.07	1.16	0.04
15	GAIL (India) Ltd.	-3.47	0.99	0.04
16	Grasim Industries Ltd.	0.8	1.08	0.03
17	HCL Technologies Ltd.	3.48	0.58	0.03
18	HDFC Bank Ltd.	15.71	0.83	0.01
19	HDFC Life Insurance Company Ltd.	7.79	0.71	0.03
20	Hero MotoCorp Ltd.	-3.81	0.98	0.03
21	Hindalco Industries Ltd.	-12.54	1.56	0.06
22	Hindustan Unilever Ltd.	17.43	0.64	0.02
23	Housing Development	10.91	1.18	0.02

	Finance Corporation Ltd.			
24	ICICI Bank Ltd.	5.16	1.45	0.04
25	ITC Ltd.	-2.31	0.89	0.02
26	Indian Oil Corporation Ltd.	3.35	1.06	0.04
27	IndusInd Bank Ltd.	3.99	1.18	0.03
28	Infosys Ltd.	7.42	0.65	0.03
29	JSW Steel Ltd.	18.9	1.28	0.04
30	Kotak Mahindra Bank Ltd.	18.27	0.97	0.02
31	Larsen & Toubro Ltd.	-3.41	1.22	0.02
32	Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd.	-4.59	1.14	0.03
33	Maruti Suzuki India Ltd.	9	1.09	0.03
34	NTPC Ltd.	-3.59	0.75	0.02
35	Nestle India Ltd.	15.79	0.49	0.02
36	Oil & Natural Gas Corporation Ltd.	-18.26	1.01	0.03
37	Power Grid Corporation of India Ltd.	3.47	0.57	0.02
38	Reliance Industries Ltd.	25.08	1.08	0.03
39	SBI Life Insurance Company Ltd.	12.35	0.46	0.03
40	Shree Cement Ltd.	15.76	0.96	0.03
41	State Bank of India	-2.91	1.53	0.05
42	Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd.	-13.21	0.81	0.04
43	Tata Consultancy Services Ltd.	9.16	0.49	0.02
44	Tata Motors Ltd.	-31.09	1.68	0.08
45	Tata Steel Ltd.	2.09	1.58	0.05
46	Tech Mahindra Ltd.	-1.1	0.65	0.03
47	Titan Company Ltd.	23.07	0.86	0.04
48	UPL Ltd.	14.6	1.06	0.04
49	UltraTech Cement Ltd.	6.37	1.12	0.03
50	Wipro Ltd.	-2.13	0.5	0.02
-	Nifty 50	3.98	1.00	0.01

Source: Computed

Interpretation

The mean return and beta values of the 50 companies chosen for the study are shown in Table 1. The return of 34 enterprises is favorable for the study period, while the return of the remaining 16 companies is negative. Among the sample companies, Bajaj Finance Ltd has the best return of 51.59 percent and Tata Motors has the lowest return of -31.09 percent. According to Sharpe, stocks with negative returns are not selected for further research.

Beta is a measure of systemic risk; a beta of larger than 1 implies that the stock is more volatile than the market index, while a beta of less than 1 indicates that it is less volatile. SBI Life Insurance Company has the lowest beta of 0.46 and Tata Motors has the highest beta of 1.68. Out of the 50 equities, 27 have a beta of less than one, while the remaining 23 have a beta of larger than one, indicating that they are more volatile than the Nifty 50 market index.

CONCLUSION

Portfolio diversity allows an investor to maximise their portfolio return while reducing risk. For both institutional and ordinary investors, putting together an optimal portfolio is a difficult undertaking. Using the Sharpe's Single Index Model, this study seeks to design an optimal portfolio by evaluating 50 stocks that make up the Nifty 50 index. When a security is part of a well-diversified portfolio, this model gives investors an indication of how risky it is. Only 8 equities out of 50 were found to be part of the ideal portfolio, indicating that they met the criterion for inclusion in the optimal portfolio. These companies' excess return to beta ratio was higher than the Single Cut-off mark. Many other general and macroeconomic factors influence the movement of a stock, therefore investors should take these into account when choosing stocks for their ideal portfolio. The stock market has consistently outperformed other investment avenues, making it an attractive investment option for investors.

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